

A Study on the Role of ICT in Securing Books in Academic Libraries

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Introduction :

Academic libraries in India are seriously suffering from book theft and mutilation. This has prompted many researchers from India to look into the matter but to no avail. Few of the research study reveal that book theft and mutilation in academic libraries in India are majorly caused by self-interest, few copies of books, poor ventilation, limited reading space and poverty. Academic libraries are facing times of unparalleled change and unprecedented challenge. Academic libraries have moved from a considerable state of innovation to a stage of necessity. Academic libraries are operating in a climate of declining budgets and increasing cost of library materials; this has led library leaders to be under pressure to secure library materials due to resource scare environment the libraries find themselves.

Electronic security systems (ICT gadgets) have been identified as a major tool that can reduce book theft and mutilation after it was tested in an academic library in America. There is also some other mechanism used in mitigating book theft and mutilation in academic libraries. However, it is highly recommended that ICT gadgets like RFID technology, heat sensor, surveillance cameras, panic alarms,

door intrusion alarms, delay devices, metal detectors are used in securing library resources. However, researcher were argued that despite the notable benefits of using ICT gadget like RFID in securing library books, and the researcher also pointed out that it is not the ultimate solution to book mutilation and theft as there are various ways to beat RFID.

Academic Library :

Academic libraries stand as educational avenues where information embedded in books and other researched documents get stored for the purpose of data access, retrieval, and analysis. In other words, academic libraries depicts as a place where researched information about specific fields could become found to further research. Academic libraries as institutions primarily constructed for “educational, cultural, research, recreational and information needs of their users”. Simply put, academic libraries offer appropriate data that span through different cultures and disciplines in order to further the research or knowledge of users. Academic libraries also affirm that they mainly provide services that involve data access, recovery, analysis, storage, conveyance, and organization.

Benefits of ICT in Libraries :

Globalization driven by ICT is presently having phenomenal impact on library practices ICTSs are significant and useful tools for sustainable development in all fields and all aspects of our society. ICTs provide means to actualizing developmental goals in education, health, agriculture, business and commerce among others. The introduction of ICTs in education had brought about computerization of traditional materials such as books, journals newspaper and other information resources in the library. This has also led to the existence of virtual library. Educational researchers, through the use of ICT can access current literature materials with ease. ICTs also encourage collaboration among researchers irrespective of their locations. Internet provides up-to-date information on any subject. Likewise, earlier research findings can be easily accessed through the internet.

ICTs enable libraries to locate store, retrieve and disseminate information. ICT tools such as CD-ROM, e-mail are used in libraries for dissemination of information. In addition, digitization of information resources which involves converting print resources to electronic form is also carried out, using ICT.

Other benefits of using ICT in Academic Libraries :

- Provision of speedy and easy access to information.
- Provision of remote and round the clock access to users.
- Provision of access to unlimited information from different sources.
- ICT enable easier, faster, cheaper and more effective library operations.

Improvement of ICT Gadget :

Information Communication Technology (ICT) has remained a catalyst in the issue of national advancement and development. Information, as power is effectively an infinite resource and a vital tool needed for the development of all sectors in any nation. It is therefore, imperative that application in libraries would go a long way in satisfying the information need of the citizens. It is worthy of note, that the emergence of ICT has impacted greatly on the quality of information provided through libraries. It also enables proper and adequate provision of library services to library users from all disciplines. In this 21st century, the drastic role of ICT in library operations cannot be over emphasized. Many library routines and operations that were initially performed manually are now being converted to computerized operations which means, applications of ICT techniques to providing better and faster services to the end users.

A nation without functional libraries and information centres may lack access to information that would enable her sustainable development. In this era of globalization, in which the world is connected, information gains its power through permanent storage and wide distribution, which could be achieved through ICT. Accordingly the world now experiences a digital scenario in which ICT has changed the possibilities of the library job promotions and has brought changes to expected library performances.

Conclusion :

Application of information communication technology in library services in the academic libraries raises the question of the depth of organization of knowledge. Uses of ICT to provision of library services are a crucial effort towards sustainable development of any country. Libraries to remain to have like agents for facilitate

sustainable development; efforts must be made to provide the right information at the right time. With the ICT in place, the objectives of libraries will not only be achieved but it will also help libraries to compete with their counterparts in the developed world. Developing countries they must also recognize ICT as key strategic tool for the development.

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